

The Poetics of Resistance: An Analysis of Language and Metaphor in the Miyah Poetry from Assam

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Abstract

In the literary domain of the Northeastern state of Assam, a collective of writers who call themselves the Miyah poets have charted a new, impactful course in recent times. Miyah poetry is a potent literary movement that has sparked political discourse and solidarity, connecting with broader struggles for rights and recognition at the national and international levels.

This brand of resistance poetry has emerged in the context of citizenship struggles in the state when the law had turned an entire community from humans beings to mere registration numbers. The so called Miyah people are descendants of Muslim peasants, who were relocated from present day Bangladesh to Assam by the British colonial powers for agricultural labour. The colonial narrative of 'foreigners' or 'illegal migrants' resulted in the pervasive "othering" of the community in the state. They have been rendered 'outsiders' in the land, and found themselves at the receiving end of years of deep seated disdain and contempt.

Through an analysis of representative *Miyah* poems, this paper attempts to explore the innovati

Keywords

Miyah Poetry, Poetics of Resistance, Subversion of Traditional Aesthetics, Language, Metaphors of Identity and Belonging.

Introduction

In the literary domain of the northeastern state of Assam, in India, a collective of writers who call themselves the Miyah poets have charted a new, impactful course in recent times. *Miyah* poetry is a potent literary movement that has sparked political discourse and solidarity, connecting with broader struggles for rights and recognition within the nation and abroad. It is a form of Resistance poetry which articulates cultural dissent against hegemonic doctrines of identity and belonging.

This brand of resistance poetry had emerged in the context of citizenship struggles in the state of Assam, when the law had turned an entire community from humans to mere registration numbers. Questions regarding citizenship became more complex in the context of the National Register of Citizens (NRC), 2016 and Citizenship Amendment Act(CAA) that deemed two million people 'stateless'.

The *Miyah* community, is formed by the descendants of Bengal-origin Muslims who inhabit the shifting, erosion-prone river islands and floodplains called char-chapori of the mighty Brahmaputra river, flowing through Assam. The so called *Miyah* people are descendants of Muslim peasants, who were relocated from erstwhile Bengal or Bangladesh to Assam by the British colonial powers for agricultural labour. The colonial narrative of 'foreigners' or 'illegal migrants' resulted in the pervasive "othering" of the community in the state. They have been rendered 'outsiders' in the land they made their home. They find themselves at the centre of political debate and encounter a deep seated disdain and contempt in the state.

Objective of study

Resistance poetry emerges from the collective consciousness of the subaltern. Such poetry in India, has historically functioned, as the "the small voice of history", articulating collective dissent through aesthetic forms that simultaneously document and resist oppression. The poetics of resistance constitute more than just thematic content - they represent an alternative philosophy that challenges dominant historiography through thematic transgression, strategic use of metaphor, intertextuality and linguistic innovation as weapons of ideological battle.

In this context, the objective of this paper is to analyse the innovative ways in which *Miyah* protest poetry from Assam challenges dominant structures of identity and belonging. The study will focus upon select works of *Miyah* Poets to see how language and metaphor are used to articulate identity, belonging and defiance of

hegemonic ideologies. It seeks to discuss how the theme and utterance of *Miyah* poetry aligns with those of the major Protest Literature Movements all around the world.

Review of Literature

Critical readings of *Miyah* poets are sparse and exist mainly on academic and scholarly articles in online journals, online news pages or blogs. Besides a few published anthologies of their works, a majority of the *Miyah* poems were circulated on social media in original and translated versions. Scholarly opinions on Resistance Literature as a whole was obtained from the works of Ranajit Guha and Gayatri Spivak, both pivotal figures in the field of Subaltern Studies. Apart from this, the literature of *Udita Bannerjee*, *Sanjib Sahoo*, *Uttaran Das Gupta* and *Shalim M Hussain* has also reviewed for this paper.

Analysis

During 2016, in the wake of protests against the National Register of Citizens (NRC), when the *Miyah* people faced discrimination and suspicion regarding their citizenship in Assam, the collective *Miyah* poets reclaimed the word in their protest poetry and a movement was born.

The earliest poem by this community, that voiced the discrimination they faced, is a poem named *Charuwar Ukti* (translated as *A Charuwa's Proposition*), written by Maulana Bande Ali in 1939. *Miyah* poetry was mostly written in Assamese or the *char-chapori* dialect until 2016, when teacher, writer and social activist Hafiz Ahmed's poem *Write Down I am a Miyah*, translated into English by poet and researcher, Shalim Hussain, went viral on Facebook , triggering the *Miyah* poetry movement.

"Write

Write down

I am a Miya

My serial number in the NRC is 200543

I have two children

Another is coming

Next summer.

Will you hate him

As you hate me?

Write I am a Miya

I turn waste, marshy lands

To green paddy fields

To feed you.

I carry bricks

To build your buildings

Drive your car

For your comfort

Clean your drain

To keep you healthy.

I have always been

In your service

And yet

You are dissatisfied!

Write down

I am a Miya,

A citizen of a democratic, secular, Republic

Without any rights
My mother a D voter,
Though her parents are Indian.
If you wish, kill me, drive me from my village,
Snatch my green fields
Hire bulldozers
To roll over me.
Your bullets
Can shatter my breast
For no crime.
Write
I am a Miya
Of the Brahmaputra
Your torture
Has burnt my body black
Reddened my eyes with fire.
Beware!
I have nothing but anger in stock
Keep away!
Or
Turn to Ashes."

In this poem, the refrain " Write down/ I am a Miyah", acts as a metaphorical act of self-inscription, of asserting one's identity. It inverts the power of state controlled documentation. The mention of the serial number in the NRC equates citizenship registers to a dehumanising cataloging system. The *Miyah* is metaphorically presented as a life-giver, who works to "feed" the nation, transforming marshy wastelands into green paddy fields by their back-breaking labour. The acts of carrying bricks, driving cars, cleaning drains collectively portray the *Miyah* as the building block of society, the unseen and unappreciated labourer.

For the *Miyah* poets, their poems speak their otherness. This is evident in their defiant embracing of the word "*Miyah*" to label themselves and their art. The term "*Miyah*", originally an Urdu term of address for a gentleman, morphed into an ethnic slur in Assam. The epithet was reclaimed by these poets as a complex and potent metaphor signifying their identity, resilience and their resistance to oppression. They proudly identified themselves as *Miyah* poets, subverting a racist barb into a badge of honour. This is a powerful literary device commonly used by resistance literature. This reappropriation of language, strips the word of its derogatory power and serves to express solidarity against racial prejudice.

Miyah poet and activist , Rehna Sultana's moving poem My Mother (2016) erases the distinction between the mother figure and the idea of the motherland, which is complicated for *Miyah* poets.

"I was dropped on your lap my mother
Just as my father, grandfather, great-grandfather
And yet you detest me, my mother,
For who I am.
Yes, I was dropped on your lap as

a cursed *Miyah*, my mother.
You can't trust me
Because I have somehow grown this
beard.
Somehow slipped into a lungi
...
I have no identity, no language
I have lost myself, lost everything
That could define me
And yet I hold you close
I try to melt into you...
Open your eyes once mother
Open your lips
Tell these sons of the earth
That we are all brothers.
And yet I tell you again
I am just another child...
Not a 'Bangladeshi'
Miyah I am,
A *Miyah*"...

In this poem too, the derogatory term *Miyah*, is repurposed to empower. By personifying the motherland as an unloving mother, Sultana complicates notions of belonging, turning personal pain into a collective cry for recognition and brotherhood. Sultana highlights physical and cultural traits weaponised against *Miyahs*, the erasure of their identity and their language. The dialect, the lungi, the beard and the cap are metaphors of identity. Yet the speaker persists in holding the motherland in her loving embrace, trying to "melt" into her. The poem not only documents pain but pleads for empathy and change. Sultana's poem infuses personal grief into collective assertion, thus creating a new narrative of inclusion. The opening lines of the poem establish a generational claim to belong.

The utterance brings into focus the theme of belonging in *Miyah* poetry, the fervent yearning to establish a kinship with the land. Shalim Hussein, writer and translator, asserts that " the theme in *Miyah* poetry is not the search for a home but to assert that this, here, is home".

Many *Miyah* poets use evocative verses to bring to light the ways in which routine ways of being Miya - their bodies, clothing, cultural practices are vilified . An instance is Kazi Neel's poem That land is Mine, I am not of that Land

"The land that makes my father an alien
That kills my brother with bullets
My sister with gang-rape
The land where my mother stokes in her heart live burning coals
That land is mine
I am not of that land
The land where my claim over a lungi is suspect
Where there are no ears for cries

Where demanding rights throws you under the plummeting fists of ghosts
Where earth is weighed and sold to Tatas, Birlas and Ambanis
That land is mine
I am not of that land
The land where a cap is radicalism
A *Miyah* sub-human
Every *charuwa* a Bangladeshi
That land is mine
I am not of that land ...”

Kazi Neel’s poem, emblematic of the *Miyah* resistance poetry, speaks of the stigmatisation of *Miyah* identity. The repetitive refrain , “That Land is Mine, I am not of that Land”, mirrors the speaker’s internal conflict and external defiance. The language is raw and accusatory, without embellishment, drawn from everyday speech to democratise resistance . It exposes the absurdity of labels, speaking the truth in plain terms. It universalises personal pain by the mention of parents and siblings. The poem turns metaphors of otherness such as “*charuwa*”, “*Miyah*” , “Bangladeshi”, into tools of solidarity and defiance.

Miyah poets try to narrate their stories on their own terms and reimagine radically inclusive notions of citizenship. Kazi Neel’s poem uses a stark, declarative voice to reclaim agency, expose systemic injustice and affirm paradoxical belonging-claiming the land while disavowing its oppressive structures. The speaker claims the “land” materially but rejects it spiritually because it kills and violates. Thereby he creates a space for a hybrid identity that defies binary citizenship. This technique echoes global resistance literature like Palestinian, Black African or Dalit poetry where the land is at once beloved and bloodied.

The driving force behind the widespread recognition received by the *Miya* poetry movement is poet, writer, translator and rights activist Shalim Hussein. His poem *Nana I have Written* , is a hard hitting piece in which the speaker declares his identity unapologetically, weaving narratives of survival, achievement and rebellion using a language that is raw and performative.

“Nana I have written attested countersigned
And been verified by a public notary
That I am a *Miyah*
Now see me rise
From flood waters
Float over landslides
March through sand and marsh and snakes
Break the earth’s will draw trenches with spades
Crawl through fields of rice and diarrhoea and
sugarcane
And a 10% literacy rate
See me shrug my shoulders curl my hair
Read two lines of poetry one formula of math
Read confusion when bullies call me
Bangladeshi
And tell my revolutionary heart
But I am a *Miyah*...

See me suited in Silicon Valley suited at McDonalds
Enslaved in Beerwa bride-trafficked in Mewat
See the stains on my childhood
The gold medals on my PhD certificate...
See me catch a plane get a Visa catch a bullet train
Catch a bullet
Catch your drift
Catch a rocket
Wear a lungi to space
And there where no one can hear you scream,
Thunder
I am Miyah
I am Proud"

The phrase "written attested countersigned/verified by public notary" ironically asserts an identity that society seeks to delegitimise. The language and metaphors - "break the earth's will", rise from flood waters", "catch a rocket", "wear a lungi to space", transform the speaker from victim to superman, breaking through oppressive structures . The command "see me" is a call to witness the resilience and accomplishments of the speaker. Metaphors are drawn from nature, labour and migration to symbolise the community's endurance and productivity. Water and land dominate as metaphors for both destruction and rebirth. The run on lines mirror the chaotic, arduous journey of displacement and labour. The style resists polished, elitist literary norms , embracing a vernacular authenticity the reflects the community's lived experiences. Cultural code-switching, mixing English, Assamese and dialect resists assimilation and preserves hybrid identities. This technique reclaims a natural, fluid identity over rigid, imposed structures.

Another poem My Son has learnt to Cuss like the City by *Miyah* poet Siraj Khan is also rooted in the lived experiences of the *Miyah* community from the chars or shifting riverine islands of the Brahmaputra

"When I leave the chars for the City
They ask, 'Oi, where is your house?'
How do I say, 'In the heart of Borogang
Amid silvery sands
Flickering between stalks of jhau grass
Where there are no roads, no chariots
Where the feet of big men seldom fall
Where the air is a grassy green
There, there is my home'.
When I leave the chars for the city
They ask, 'Oi, what is your language?'
Just as the tongues of beasts and birds
Have no books, my language has no school
I draw a tune from my mother's mouth
And sing Bhatiyali. I match rhythm with rhythm
Pain with pain

Clasp the sounds of the land close to my heart
And speak the whispers of the sand
The language of earth is the same everywhere...
They try to scare me, 'Oi, when did you come here?'
I came from no 'somewhere'
When Bajan left the chars for the city
With a bundle of jute leaves on his head
The police jumped on him without reason
And the examination
Of pieces of paper began..."

In this poem, everyday language which is colloquial and rhythmic, serves as a form of resistance against standardised forms of expression. The poem's structure eschews formal rhyme or meter for a free-flowing repetitive cadence that echoes folk songs such as the "Bhatiyali" or traditional boatman's song from the chars. The orality of the language akin to "the tongues of beasts and birds", with no "school" and "no books", positions it as an innate, inherited knowledge passed through generations. This suggests that the speakers dialect is as legitimate and natural as the sounds of wildlife. It is the language of the landscape, emerging from sands, from their pain signifying a complete identification with the land. The blending of sensory, earthy diction "grassy green", "whispers of the sand" with confrontational phrases, the poem resists assimilation, asserting that marginalised language are not deficient but vibrant- "The language of the earth is the same everywhere".

In *Miyah* poetry, the metaphors are drawn heavily from nature symbolising a free and fluid existence, ever changing like the shifting sandbars the *Miyah* populace inhabit, but at the same time, resilient. The image of "Home" amid the "silvery sands" and the "stalks of jhau grass" with no roads, evoke a transient landscape that defies mapping or ownership. This metaphor resists urban notions of rigidly demarcated properties by framing home as an emotional, ecological space untouched by urban systems. It highlights the absurdity of borders for those who came from "no 'somewhere'" - a metaphor for the rootless, shifting identities shaped by rivers. The "bundle of jute", a hardy crop, signifies the resilience of the community. A symbol of poverty is here turned into one of quiet defiance.

The poems emerge from their destitution and angst because only this hold the promise of a return, of homecoming. The Journey by Kazi Neel is a vivid and powerful poem of homecoming. The Journey motif is central to the *Miyah* experience which is a perilous, unending one through displacement and survival.

" I will have to cross a vast sea of anguish
And I will have to traverse a slippery century
like an even powerful monster
I have given her my word
I will come with the taste of wet rain in my heart"

Miyah poetry is rooted in memories of home and spaces we identify as own.

While returning home may not be politically or geographically possible for many in the *Miyah* community, these artistic expressions retain the architecture of a homeland.

Conclusion

The distinctiveness of *Miyah* poetry lies in its deliberate departure from conventional poetic norms of structure and form. In the true tradition of Resistance Literature, *Miyah* protest poetry too, has developed unique strategies of linguistic subversion, thematic transgression and performative resistance.

In their insistence to be included in Assamese society, *Miyah* poets have created an inclusive idiom. They draw from native dialects because, as Shalim Hussain says, there are certain lived experiences in the real world that cannot be replicated in English or Assamese, for instance, " the sound of an earthworm

crawling through the mud". Protest poetry often uses local languages to express their lived experiences. There is a rhythm to *Miyah* poetry that comes from an amalgamation of folk songs, local dialects and contemporary Assamese poetry. The poems mimic the spoken word, making it performative and communal- ideal for resistance poetry which is often shared in protests or on online platforms.

Miyah poetry uses language and metaphor to invert power dynamics. By romanticising the ephemerality of the chars, of sands that whisper, the poems resist erasure, affirming cultural continuity amid migration and violence. It echoes traditions like Dalit, Black, Palestinian or Postcolonial poetry where subaltern voices weaponise simple living and thinking against complexity.

The lyrics of belonging are set against the lush green rice fields, golden jute crops, diverse wildlife, vibrant harvest festivals and the river. The poems not only draw attention to the indignities suffered by the community but they do much more: they speak of life in the *char-chapori*, the joys and sorrows of living in the shifting sandbars and floodplains of the Brahmaputra. The stark images from the daily lives of the *Miyah* people bring into sharp focus the man made discriminations and the challenges posed by nature.

Miyah poetry also draws heavily from their experiences with the soil and water bodies. Their poetry is rich in metaphors related to the land, to agriculture, to labour and the mighty Brahmaputra river flowing through it. Rivers play a very significant role in *Miyah* poetry, as spaces of imagination and also as metaphors. The association with the river is complex. There is immense respect for the sacredness and the power of the river to cause havoc. *Miyah* poetry counters the racist allegations with new metaphors by highlighting the traditional relationship of the marginalised community with the riverine environment. The state projects the community to be damaging the environment and issues violent evictions. Evocation of traditional environmental relations serves the purpose of healing and rehumanising themselves.

Finally, It is a poetry that is deeply personal but taps into the universal in us. *Miyah* poetry is about the human condition as any other poetry in any language.

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